

IGRINS Brings High-Resolution Near-IR Spectroscopy Back to Gemini South

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Through the Visiting Instrument Program, international Gemini Observatory users now have access to a powerful capability at the Gemini South telescope (Gemini Observatory is a Program of NSF's NOIRLab). The Immersion GRating INfrared Spectrometer (IGRINS) is a cross-dispersed near-infrared spectrograph with a resolving power of $R = 45,000$ covering the H and K windows (1.45–2.5 microns), yielding both broad spectral coverage and high spectral resolution in a single exposure.

IGRINS has a strong track record of diverse and innovative science results, having spent over 350 nights at the McDonald Observatory in Texas and 200 nights at the Discovery Channel Telescope (now the Lowell Discovery

Telescope) at Lowell Observatory in Arizona. Recent results span a range of topics from cold molecular clouds and diffuse interstellar bands to T Tauri stars, systems containing multiple stars and/or planets, and even microquasars. The response to IGRINS at Gemini has been extremely strong, resulting in a large number of successful proposals for its inaugural visit in the 2018A semester and again on its return in 2020.

As a Visiting Instrument, IGRINS is ideal because it has a single observing mode and contains no moving parts. By exchanging the input optics to accommodate Gemini, the IGRINS H and K echellograms are unchanged between facilities. For the first visit, the instrument team accompanied IGRINS to Gemini South in March 2018, installed and tested it, and then provided support for Gemini User Community observations with the help of Gemini staff for a total of 50 nights, resulting in excellent science that is starting to appear in journals now. The team also provided a data reduction pipeline to assist users.

Following the tremendous success of that visit, a much longer return visit was negotiated, and we are now excited to have IGRINS at Gemini South for six semesters, beginning with 2020A. This is perfect timing for Gemini, as we are expecting to get our very own IGRINS-2 Facility Instrument in a few years, and so for this reason, we have moved IGRINS from the status of normal Visiting Instrument to that of "Transitional Instrument." We are using IGRINS to train

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Gemini staff in the use of IGRINS-2, which helps them contribute to discussions of the minor upgrades that may be possible to implement in the IGRINS-2 design over the next year. Gemini staff are also able to make use of this time to begin integrating IGRINS into the Gemini software and operations planning strategies so that we can hit the ground running when IGRINS-2 arrives.

To learn more about the design of IGRINS, and to find out what you need to know to propose for this unique instrument on Gemini South, see <https://sites.google.com/site/igrinsatgemini/proposing-and-observing> and see the following SPIE papers: Yuk et al. (7735M, 2010), Park et al. (91471D, 2014), and Mace et al. (99080C, 2016).

The modified ballast weight assembly waiting in Chile to attach IGRINS to the Gemini South telescope, with SOAR gracing the scenery in the background. (Credit: international Gemini Observatory/NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/B. Chinn)

Figure 3: The IGRINS Team (Heeyoung Oh, Kimberly Sokal, and Ricardo Lopez) at UT Austin packing the instrument for shipping. (Credit: UT Austin/G. Mace)

Figure 4: IGRINS and Gemini team collaboration during a site visit to Gemini South (Huihyun Kim, Brian Chinn, Kimberly Sokal, Greg Mace, and John Good). (Credit: UT Austin/K. Sokal)

Figure 5: The IGRINS spectrograph slit (white bar) and a graduated scale used to measure optical performance. Lines resolved well below the slit width show that IGRINS optics for Gemini will perform as designed and sensitivity will be optimized.

For more exciting science produced by IGRINS at Gemini South, please see the following publications:

- Hinkle, K. H., Fekel, F. C., Joyce, R. R., et al., “Infrared Spectroscopy of Symbiotic Stars. XII. The Neutron Star SyXB System 4U 1700+24 = V934 Herculis,” 2019, *ApJ*, 872, 43
- Kidder, B., Mace, G., Sokal, K., et al., “Radial Velocities of Low-mass Candidate TWA Members,” 2019, *ApJ*, 879, 63
- López-Valdivia, R., Mace, G. N., Sokal, K. R., et al., “Effective Temperatures of Low-Mass Stars from High-Resolution H-band Spectroscopy,” 2019, *ApJ*, 879, 105
- Tegler, S. C., Stufflebeam, T. D., Grundy, W. M., et al., “A New Two-Molecule Combination Band as a Diagnostic of Carbon Monoxide Diluted in Nitrogen Ice on Triton,” 2019, *AJ*, 158, 17

IGRINS is a collaboration of the University of Texas and the Korea Astronomy and Space Science Institute (KASI). Daniel Jaffe of UT Austin is the Principal Investigator, and Chan Park of KASI is deputy PI and KASI instrument PI. Jae-Joon Lee at KASI supervises the IGRINS operational program on the Korean side. The first IGRINS visit to Gemini was supported by the US National Science Foundation under grant AST-1702267 (PI Gregory Mace, University of Texas at Austin) and by the Korean GMT Project of KASI.